

Network analysis of host response to SARS-CoV-2 reveals a new set of genes with therapeutic and long term implications for COVID-19 disease.

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Summary

The COVID-19 disease led to an unprecedented health emergency, still ongoing worldwide. Given the lack of a vaccine or a clear therapeutic strategy to counteract the infection as well as its secondary effects, there is currently a pressing need to generate new insights into the SARS-CoV-2 induced host response. Biomedical data can help to investigate new aspects of the COVID-19 pathogenesis, but source heterogeneity represents a major drawback and limitation. In this work, we apply data integration methods to develop a Unified Knowledge Space (UKS) and use it to identify a new set of genes associated with SARS-CoV-2 host response, both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Functional analysis of these genes reveals possible long term systemic effects of the infection, such as vascular remodelling and fibrosis. Finally, we identified a set of potentially interesting drugs targeting proteins involved in multiple steps of the host response to the virus.

Keywords

COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, coronavirus, virus-host interaction, unified knowledge space, data integration, multi-layer network analysis, drug targeting, drug repositioning.

Introduction

The newly identified coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 is responsible for a pandemic form of respiratory tract infection currently ongoing worldwide. Even if most patients remain asymptomatic or show mild symptoms, some develop complications, such as severe pneumonia and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) (Girija et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2020). Furthermore, systemic complications, such as cardiovascular disorders, persistent lung injuries and possibly fibrosis are rapidly emerging as key threats in addition to the respiratory syndrome. Restrictive measures have been adopted to slow down the spreading of the virus, however, it is expected that the infection will remain entrenched in the population for years (O'Neill and Netea, 2020).

To date, no vaccine is yet available and a number of therapeutic strategies have been proposed to control the clinical outcomes of the infection (Jeong et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2020). Currently, a great effort is being made by the scientific community in order to develop new therapeutic approaches as well as to understand the molecular events characterising the host response to SARS-CoV-2 infection. SARS-CoV-2 infects the cells *via* the angiotensin converting enzyme 2 (*ACE2*) receptor-mediated endocytosis (Matricardi et al., 2020). *ACE2* is expressed in several organs and cell types, such as lung, heart, kidney, intestine and endothelial cells, which further raises concerns about possible ectopic effects of the infection (Varga et al., 2020).

Molecular characterisation of infected tissues and cells can elucidate key potential molecular targets involved in the pathogenesis of COVID-19. To this end, for instance, Gordon *et al.* applied mass spectrometry to identify SARS-CoV-2 human protein interactors (Gordon et al., 2020). Moreover, transcriptomic data of infected lungs and cell types are already publicly available, and can help in elucidating key molecular alterations characterizing the COVID-19 disease (Blanco-Melo et al., 2020). Nonetheless, a knowledge gap exists to understand the molecular events linking the early host responses to the virus with the late phenotypic alterations. This gap could be filled by exploiting the large amount of biomedical data accumulated in recent years. However, the use of this information is currently hampered by the heterogeneity of data formats scattered across multiple repositories (Manzoni et al., 2018; Tadist et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019).

In this study, we applied scalable and flexible data integration methods to develop a robust compendium of molecular knowledge, the Unified Knowledge Space (UKS), by linking and analysing data across a multitude of domains and repositories. We define the UKS as a multilayer network, where nodes and edges can be of any type, such as genes, gene products and drugs (Boccaletti et al., 2014; Kivelä et al., 2014).

We systematically analyzed the UKS and identified a set of genes that can explain the kinetic responses to SARS-CoV-2 and can be further investigated as new therapeutic targets. Furthermore, the functional characterization of this new set of genes allows us to describe possible unpredicted long term complications of the COVID-19 disease, as well as to suggest repositioning of some already approved drugs.

Results and discussion

A novel set of genes involved in the pathogenesis of COVID-19 can be retrieved from multi-scale molecular network analysis

The Unified knowledge space (UKS) defined in this work has been generated by integrating multiple data sets containing protein-protein interaction (PPI) information as well as drug target relationships. By querying the UKS, we derived a network of 20,793 human protein coding genes, represented as nodes, and 132,244 edges, representing the physical interaction relationships existing between the proteins encoded by the UKS gene nodes. These interactions were integrated from four data sources and stored in the UKS together with a data support score, representing the number of sources in which the connections are present. In order to have a reliable structure of the network, we selected only edges supported in at least three out of four sources (see section “UKS Construction and PPI Network Retrieval” for more details). The UKS network was further extended with gene-drug information by adding 7,099 drug nodes that are linked to their target gene nodes through 22,973 edges (Figure 1A). We systematically mapped the SARS-CoV-2 physical interacting (PI) genes (Gordon et al, hereafter denoted as PI gene set) and the differentially expressed (DE) genes in multiple biological systems infected by SARS-CoV-2 (Blanco-Melo et al.), hereafter denoted as DE gene set onto the UKS (Figure 1B).

Figure 1: Scheme of the analytical framework: data from multiple PPI sources was collected, mapped to their corresponding Ensembl Gene IDs and integrated together with drug-target information into the UKS (A left). A robust gene-gene network is extracted from the UKS, where only edges are included that are supported by at least 3 of the merged PPI networks (A right). PI and DE genes are mapped onto the extracted gene-gene network and intermediate genes (IN) are identified by means of shortest paths between each possible pair of PI and DE (B). Pathway enrichment analysis is performed for all three gene sets and pathways specific of the IN gene set are retrieved. Drugs that have targets in all three gene sets (PI, DE and IN) are selected and classified as “high interest drugs” (C).

A set of human proteins has been recently described by Gordon *et al.* as physical interactors of the SARS-CoV-2 viral components (Gordon *et al.*, 2020). We considered these as the first set of proteins involved in the host response to a SARS-CoV-2 infection. On the other hand, we considered the differentially expressed genes retrieved from transcriptomic analysis of infected *in vivo* (infected vs healthy human lung biopsies) and *in vitro* (infected vs mock CALU-3, A549, A549 overexpressing *ACE2*, and NHBE cell lines) systems, as late effectors associated with the COVID-19 pathological phenotype. In order to identify the relationships between the first interactors of SARS-CoV-2 (PI gene set) and the late effectors (DE gene set), a third set of genes, located in the shortest path between each possible pair of (PI-DE genes) was retrieved. For each *in vitro* and *in vivo* system analyzed, we named as intermediate genes (IN gene set), all the genes, not belonging to either the PI nor the DE gene sets, significantly overrepresented ($p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$) in the shortest paths.

Figure 2: Number of known gene sets (DE and PI) and new gene set (IN) in each biological system. The number of differentially expressed genes (DE), and the new retrieved set of intermediate genes (IN), is compared in each in vitro and in vivo system. The samples derived from of a transcriptomics dataset comprising a lung biopsy and four different cell lines infected with the virus: the transformed cell lines A549 and CALU-3, the epithelial cell line NHBE and A549 overexpressing the angiotensin receptor *ACE2* (A549_ACE2).

In contrast with the heterogeneity of the DE gene set sizes, the number of intermediate genes is comparable among the different biological systems (Figure 2). Overall, we observe a progressive increase in the size of the gene sets when going from the first interactors (PI), through the intermediate genes (IN), to the effector pathways genes (DE), suggesting the role of the intermediate genes in propagating the host response mechanisms to the virus entry. The human bronchial epithelial cells (NHBE), on the contrary, was the only dataset showing a decreasing trend from the PI to the DE gene set. This is probably due to the smaller number of differentially expressed genes, which can be associated with the lower permissiveness of the NHBE cell line.

Functional characterization of intermediate gene set reveals possible long term effects of COVID-19 disease

In order to characterize the IN gene set, we performed pathway enrichment analysis independently for each *in vivo* and *in vitro* biological system analyzed. Moreover, we compared the pathways over-represented in the IN set with the ones over-represented in the PI and DE genes, respectively, in order to identify specific biological functions which could fill the gap between the early molecular interaction events and the downstream transcriptomic host response (Figure 3).

As expected, PI genes specifically enriched pathways related to viral infections, such as *Ebola Virus pathway on Host* and *Dual hijack model of Vif in HIV infection*. Not surprisingly, cilia associated pathways were also enriched, since epithelial cells are the first ones to encounter SARS-CoV-2 in the respiratory system. These pathways are also well represented in the IN genes, while they are not significantly enriched in the DE gene set.

Metabolic pathways are present in all the gene sets (PI, IN, and DE). In detail, oxidative phosphorylation and lipid metabolism were the most affected functions. Viral infections are known to induce a global metabolic alteration of the cell and, in particular, lipids play a pivotal role in facilitating viral replication (Martín-Acebes et al., 2013).

DE genes specifically enriched immune system related pathways, which were not represented in the PI gene set and minorly represented in the IN set. Some of the main effector molecules involved in the cytokine storm observed in COVID-19 were present in the enriched immune pathways (e.g. $INF\gamma$, TNF, $IL-1\beta$ and other chemokines) as well as the *NFkB transcription factor pathway* (Figure 3) (Matricardi et al., 2020; Vabret et al., 2020). Interestingly, interferon response was retrieved as significantly over-represented both in IN and DE genes. However, type I interferon was peculiarly enriched in the IN set, whereas type II was enriched in the DE set only. Interferon gamma, the only type II interferon, is one of the genes involved in the cytokine storm (Vabret et al., 2020). On the contrary, type I interferons are key antiviral mediators, and low levels have been described in COVID-19 patients (Acharya et al., 2020).

Both IN and DE genes enriched pathways related to cell differentiation, such as *lung fibrosis*, *Wnt pathway* and *ectoderm differentiation*. As we already reported, COVID-19 disease shares many mediators of the lung fibrosis pathogenesis, such as *NFkB*, *IL-6*, *TGF* and *INF* (Kinaret et al., 2020 Nano Today, *in press*). Furthermore, the receptor *ACE2* is a known anti-fibrotic mediator, and lung fibrosis has already been reported subsequently to the outbreak of SARS-CoV (Zuo et al., 2010), making it a plausible long term consequence of SARS-CoV-2 viral infection as well. IN genes specifically enriched the *Wnt pathway*, which has been linked to chronic lung pathologies, including idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, pulmonary arterial hypertension, asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (Baarsma and Königshoff, 2017). Altogether, this suggests that fibrogenic alterations in the lung can

be a possible long term effect of the COVID-19 pathogenesis (Kinaret et al. Nano Today, *in press*).

Finally, the IN gene set enriched specific biological functions not represented in PI nor DE. Signalling related pathways, with the exception of nuclear receptors, are only present in the IN group. This indicates the central role of the IN genes in propagating the signal from the PI initial interactors to the late effector pathways. Consistently, mRNA processing pathways are only enriched in the IN group.

Therefore, the pathway enrichment of the newly identified IN set of genes reveals specific categories that represent signalling and metabolic pathways. These intermediate pathways are filling the gap between the first interactors and the late effector pathways, as well as cell differentiation pathways, suggesting possible long term lung tissue remodelling.

Figure 3: pathway enrichment of the PI, IN and DE gene sets. For each biological system, statistically significant Wikipathways have been reported and the number of samples that enriched specific pathways are stated by marking them with different colours (values). Furthermore, the enriched pathways have been grouped according to more generic biological processes.

The Intermediate genes are also linked to endothelial cells dysfunction and vascular remodelling.

Interestingly, the IN gene set enriched vascular related pathways. Among them, we found *VEGF signaling pathways*, *angiogenesis*, *EPO signaling*, and extracellular matrix related pathways. Ackermann *et al.* recently showed that lung tissue of SARS-CoV-2 infected patients presented endothelial damage and significant new vessel growth (Ackermann *et al.*, 2020). The overall modulation of vascular related pathways highlighted in the IN genes, as well as the previously described cell differentiation pathways, may be an indication of endothelial remodelling and dysfunction. Endothelial dysfunction refers to a systemic condition in which the endothelium loses its physiological properties, including the tendency to promote vasodilation, fibrinolysis, and platelets aggregation (Hadi *et al.*, 2005). Different studies already proposed the endothelium as one of the main targets of SARS-CoV-2 (Huertas *et al.*, 2020; Lemke and Silverman, 2020; Sardu *et al.*, 2020), furthermore increasing evidence of coagulation alterations and fibrotic lesions are currently emerging in the scientific literature (George *et al.*, 2020; Lemke and Silverman, 2020). Therefore, the new set of IN genes further strengthens the notion that the endothelial cells play a pivotal role in the COVID-19 disease, and can help predicting long term effects in the lung in terms of vascular remodeling and dysfunction.

We further compiled five ranked lists of intermediate genes (for each *in vitro* and *in vivo* system represented in the DE space), according to the frequency in which they occurred in the list of shortest paths identified in each biological system. To obtain a final consensus rank, we merged the lists by using the Borda method (Supplementary Table 1).

Leucine-rich repeat kinase 2 (*LRRK2*) is the most frequently visited gene in the shortest paths identified in the UKS network. This gene, which has been extensively studied for its role in Parkinson disease (Li *et al.*, 2014), is known to upregulate the transcriptional activity of *NFkB* by increasing phosphorylation levels of *NFkB* inhibitor alpha (*IkB α*). Hongge *et al.* proposed that *LRRK2* has the potential to be an important target for the treatment of endothelial dysfunction (Hongge *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, Marker *et al.* demonstrated that in *HIV* infection, *LRRK2* decreases the levels of the angiogenesis inhibitor *BAI1*, and increases the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines and phagocytosis (Marker *et al.*, 2012). Given the pivotal role of *NFkB* in the COVID-19 disease, *LRRK2* is potentially important in both acute and long term responses.

Cullin 3 (*CUL3*), the third gene in the rank, has a role in endothelial remodelling and angiogenesis, both in physiological and pathological conditions (Sakaue *et al.*, 2017).

The Exportin 1 (*XPO1*) gene is known to modulate the activity of Mothers against decapentaplegic homolog 3 (*SMAD3*), a well-established initiator of epithelial mesenchymal transition (EMT) (Pan et al., 2018). *SMAD3* is an important downstream transcription factor of *TGF-beta*, which regulates the transcription of extracellular matrix components involved in cellular infection (Gough, 2015). Interestingly, *XPO1*, together with *SMAD3* and *TGF-beta*, are strongly linked to lung fibrosis (Bruccoleri et al., 2019; Walton et al., 2017). Similarly, Heat shock protein family A (*Hsp70*) member 4 (*HSPA4*), a chaperone protein, modulates the expression of transcription factor *TWIST1*, a master regulator of morphogenesis and epithelial mesenchymal transition (Park et al., 2015).

The histone variant *H2AX*, a sensitive marker of DNA repair machinery, is also present among the top genes of the Borda ranking. There is evidence that it plays an important role in endothelial cell proliferation under hypoxia and, more generally, in hypoxia-induced-angiogenesis.

The Heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoprotein A1 (*hnRNPA1*) gene has the capability of controlling migration, proliferation and gene expression levels of vascular smooth muscle cells. A recent functional study showed that not only *hnRNPA1* is an important regulator in vascular smooth muscle cells function and lesion-induced vessel remodeling, but may also represent a potential therapeutic target (Zhang et al., 2017).

Finally, during lung epithelium infection, an important role in activating both the innate and adaptive immune system and the tissue repair mechanisms, is also played by the estrogen receptor (Suba, 2020). Furthermore, anti-inflammatory effects of estrogens have already been reported (Kim et al., 2014), and are also supported by our results since both estrogen receptors *ESR1* and *ESR2* are contained in the top ranked genes (Supplementary Table 1). Based on our results, our novel UKS is able to highlight key genes involved in possible long term effects of SARS-CoV-2, involved in vascular remodelling and endothelial dysfunction, and are interesting therapeutic targets.

Drugs targeting genes in all gene sets suggest repositioning of drugs with anti-angiogenic and immuno-modulatory properties

Given the functional importance of the IN gene set, we further investigated whether these genes could also be molecular targets of known drugs. We retrieved information about drugs targeting the PI, IN and DE gene sets from the UKS.

Highlighting drugs, which can simultaneously target multiple components of the host (PI, IN, and DE gene sets) allows to uncover possible therapeutic strategies which can more effectively reduce the clinical consequences of the viral infection (Altay et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020). We hence identified 77 drugs targeting genes in all the three gene sets of interest (Figure 4 and Supplementary Table 2).

Among the 77 drugs, four different categories were strongly represented: HDAC inhibitors, proteasome inhibitors, drugs targeting the coagulation cascade and drugs targeting the opioids receptors (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Overview of the 77 drugs targeting genes in all gene sets (PI, IN, DE). The 77 retrieved drugs belong to four main therapeutic classes: HDAC inhibitors (12%), proteasome inhibitors (5%), drugs targeting the opioids receptors (16%), and the coagulation cascade (13%).

Moreover, we found cough suppressants, such as Dextromethorphan, hydrocodone and Pentoxyverine, as well as expectorants and bronchodilators, such as Theophylline, Aminophylline and Oxtriphylline (Zhou et al., 2020). These drugs are all centrally acting agents, thus exerting their effect on the lungs by inhibiting the cough centre in the brain.

Other well-represented drug categories are analgesics, antipsychotics and opioid antagonists. Haloperidol, Amitriptyline, Pentazocine and Naltrexone, among others, belong to such categories. These drugs, together with the previously described Dextromethorphan, Hydrocodone and Pentoxyverine, share the same molecular target both in the PI and IN gene sets: the sigma non-opioid intracellular receptor 1 (*SIGMAR1*) and the μ opioid receptor (*OPRM1*), respectively (Supplementary Table 2). Opioid drugs have a well recognised effect on immune cells both modulating the immune system and exerting anti-inflammatory properties (Franchi et al., 2019). Beside, existing literature suggests that opioids might be able to interact with viral receptors, viral proteins, viral promoters and even modulate epigenetic mechanisms, such as the expression of anti-viral miRNAs (Tahamtan et al., 2016). In fact,

Dextromethorphan was already reported by Gordon *et al.*, because of its antiviral properties. On the other hand, Dextromethorphan also shows immunomodulatory effects by decreasing *NF- κ B* and the *MAPK* cascade genes activation in LPS-treated dendritic cells, and interfering with primary T-cell responses (Chen *et al.*, 2013a). On the contrary, Naltrexone, an antagonist of the μ receptor, has been shown to revert the immunomodulatory action of opioids in several experimental models (Rousseaux and Greene, 2015). Since the sigma receptors have negligible affinity for Naltrexone, it might be speculated that a significant part of the effect is exerted *via* direct binding to the opioid receptors. Taken together, these data suggest that compounds acting on the sigma opioid receptors might be involved in the innate and adaptive immunity in response to a SARS-CoV-2 infection and that they can have an effect in modulating the cytokine storm observed in the most severe and life-threatening stages of the disease.

Fostamatinib, a tyrosine kinase inhibitor, is also present in the list of identified drugs and importantly it targets *LRRK2*, the most commonly crossed IN genes in the shortest paths derived from the UKS. Fostamatinib is currently used to treat autoimmune diseases and thrombocytopenia, but it has recently been proposed for COVID-19 disease treatment by Saha *et al.* (Saha *et al.*, 2020). Similarly to Fostamatinib, we retrieved several drugs targeting the coagulation cascade, such as Kappadione, a vitamin K analogue, and Menadione, used in hypoprothrombinemia treatment. It has already been shown that COVID-19 patients commonly show thrombocytopenia and are at risk of developing disseminated intravascular coagulation, even though the molecular mechanisms have been poorly described (Boccia *et al.*, 2020; Giannis *et al.*, 2020). Thrombocytopenia is usually associated with an excessive activation of platelets and of the coagulation cascade, which can be triggered upon viral infection. Indeed, viruses have the ability of altering the balance between procoagulant and anticoagulant homeostatic mechanisms, as well as to induce pathogenic processes such as endothelial dysfunction, Toll-like receptor activation, and tissue-factor pathway inhibitor activation (Giannis *et al.*, 2020; Subramaniam and Scharrer, 2018).

Noteworthy, the drugs list in Table S2 highlighted possible repositioning of *HDAC* inhibitors. *HDAC* inhibitors are a class of compounds that act on epigenetic regulation of gene expression by increasing the lysine acetylation of histones (Eckschlager *et al.*, 2017). They have antiviral properties by controlling the virus replication cycle and exerting cytotoxic activity, but they also have immunomodulatory properties by regulating the production of cytokines as well as the activity of macrophages and dendritic cells (Herbein and Wendling, 2010; Schotterl *et al.*, 2015). Gordon *et al.* showed that the SARS-CoV-2 non-structural protein 5 (Nsp5) interacts with the histone deacetylases and proposed Valproic acid as a therapeutic agent in COVID-19 (Gordon *et al.*, 2020). Our UKS system was able to detect several *HDAC* inhibitors, including Valproic acid (among Romidepsin, Belinostat, Entinostat, Tacedinaline, Fimepinostat, Panobinostat, Cucd-101), which target genes in all the PI, IN and DE sets. Specifically, the eight *HDAC* inhibitors

targeted the *HDAC2* gene present in the PI set, and the *HDAC5*, *HDAC7* and *HDAC11* present in the IN gene list, and *HDAC9*, *HDAC1*, *HDAC10*, *HDAC3*, *HDAC6*, *HDAC8* in the DE set. *HDAC2* is a class I inhibitor located in the nucleus of the cell, where it can modulate inflammation in macrophages and monocytes by inhibiting the *NFκB* complex (Ito et al., 2004). On the contrary, *HDAC5* is a class II inhibitor, which can migrate into the nucleus upon phosphorylation and mediate important anti-inflammatory functions (Fuchikami et al., 2016). Thalidomide and its derivatives, Pomalidomide and Lenalidomide, also share *HDAC2* as a molecular target. Thalidomide is an immunomodulatory agent and works by a number of mechanisms including the stimulation of T cells as well as decreasing *TNF* production. Importantly, these compounds also share anti-angiogenic properties and inhibit the proliferation of endothelial vascular cells (Giuliani et al., 2011).

Moreover, we identified proteasome inhibitors, sharing both antiviral and anti-angiogenic activity (Schneider et al., 2019). The ubiquitin-proteasome system plays an important role in virus replication and cell cycle, thus inhibiting virus entry, genome replication and viral protein synthesis. Proteasome inhibitors have already been pointed out as therapeutic strategies against other coronaviruses, since they can also limit the cytokine storm associated with the abnormal immunological response induced by the virus (Longhitano et al., 2020). Most proteasome inhibitors can inhibit the *NFκB*-mediated production of *IL-6*, and, by inhibiting the *NFκB* transcription factor, they also exert an important anti-angiogenic effect (Almond and Cohen, 2002). Remarkably, *HDAC* inhibitors, proteasome inhibitors and Thalidomide derivatives are all currently used as a therapeutic regimen against multiple myeloma, an oncological condition in which myeloma cells produce a microenvironment enriched with pro-angiogenic factors, such as *VEGF* and *IL-6* (Giuliani et al., 2011). In conclusion, the four classes of drugs identified by the UKS share both immunomodulatory and anti-angiogenic properties, and are therefore good candidates in counteracting both the acute cytokine storm as well as endothelial and vascular complications.

Conclusions

Characterizing the cascade of events taking place at multiple levels in response to SARS-CoV-2 infection is urgently needed as the COVID-19 pandemic keeps rampaging worldwide. Here we interrogate a unified network of public biomedical data, the Unified Knowledge Space (UKS), in order to elucidate the molecular alterations characterizing the SARS-CoV-2 infection.

By assuming that early viral responses are mediated by virus-interacting genes and the downstream effects of infection by genes whose expression is altered, we interrogated the UKS in search of a novel set of intermediate genes that would help to further characterize the COVID-19 pathogenesis. Our analysis highlights genes

representing functions related to fibrosis and vascular remodelling, implying further long term consequences of SARS-CoV-2 infection. Furthermore, we identified a set of drugs with at least one target present in each of the identified gene sets: proteins known to interact with SARS-CoV-2 (PI, as defined by Gordon et al.(Gordon et al., 2020)), differentially expressed (DE) genes in multiple biological systems infected by SARS-CoV-2 (Blanco-Melo et al.) and intermediate genes (IN, newly discovered here). Our results point to therapeutic classes with immunomodulatory and anti-angiogenic roles.

In conclusion, the robust multilayer network-based approach developed here helps to shed light on the details of the SARS-CoV-2-host interaction, suggesting possible long term effects of the viral infections, and highlights important therapeutic targets, paving the way to new drug repositioning studies. Furthermore, due to the high flexibility of the UKS, our strategy can be applied to study the molecular alterations induced by other diseases or by the exposure to drugs or chemicals.

Methods

The proposed methodology aims at giving insights into the possible mechanistic aspects of the SARS-CoV-2 infection and host response through the construction of a Unified Knowledge Space. Combining knowledge about human viral interaction proteins, their physical interactors and transcriptomic studies into a single knowledge space allows to gain new valuable insights about the mechanisms underlying Covid-19. By further expanding the UKS with information about drug targets, pathways and associated functions, valuable novel knowledge regarding multiple facets of the SARS-CoV-2 infections can be generated. We define the UKS as a multilayer network, where nodes and edges can be of any data type and edges represent different known relationships between nodes of one data type or between multiple data types (Boccaletti et al., 2014; Kivela et al., 2014). For this study the UKS is constructed based on known Protein-Protein-Interactions as well as drug-gene target relationships. The UKS comprises all human protein-coding genes as retrieved from Ensembl (Hunt et al., 2018), known physical interactions of their associated proteins as well as all known drug target relationships.

Data Collection

Viral Interactors

Genes known to be physically interacting with the viral components of SARS-CoV-2 were retrieved from (Gordon et al., 2020). These genes are involved in the first events of the host response upon viral infection.

Transcriptomics data

The gene expression data of human lung biopsies of SARS-Cov-2 infected patients and SARS-Cov-2 infected cell lines were retrieved from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) repository (GEO ID GSE147507) (Blanco-Melo et al., 2020). In this work we analyzed five different experimental conditions: human lung biopsies of SARSCov-2 infected patients and uninfected control; A549 cell line infected with SARS-Cov-2, A549 cell line infected with SARS-Cov-2 overexpressing *ACE2*; Calu-3 cells infected with SARS-Cov-2; NHBE cell line infected with SARS-Cov-2. For each of the cell lines the mock treated lines were collected to be used as controls for the expression analysis.

Transcriptomics data analysis (DE gene set identification)

Gene expression analysis was carried out starting from the raw counts provided within the GEO record. Low read counts were filtered by applying the proportion test method implemented within the NOISeq Bioconductor package (Tarazona et al., 2011). Filtered counts were normalized through the upper quartile method implemented in the NOISeq package. Differential expression analysis was carried out by using the DESeq2 Bioconductor package (Love et al., 2014), while p-values were adjusted through the Benjamini-Hochberg method (Benjamini and Hochberg, 1995).

UKS Construction and PPI Network Retrieval

Known human protein coding genes were retrieved from Ensembl (Assembly: GRCh38) (Hunt et al., 2018), which represent the base of the developed UKS. Known Protein-Protein-Interactions were retrieved from HIPPIE (Alanis-Lobato et al., 2017), HitPredict (López et al., 2015; Patil et al., 2011), KEGG (Kanehisa et al., 2017) and STRING (Szklarczyk et al., 2019). In order to construct a high robust and high-quality network, the four data sources were merged into a single Protein-Protein-Interaction network, while source information is encoded in their relationships. Proteins are mapped to their associated genes, which represent nodes of the merged network, while known protein-protein interactions are represented as edges of the network. The edges were weighted based on an interaction source support score, where an edge weight of 1 indicates source support by 100% of the collected sources. Drug target information was collected from Drugbank (Wishart et al., 2018) and Open Targets (Koscielny et al., 2017) and integrated into the UKS. The data contained in these two sources is merged into a single data layer by means of mapping drugs to PubChem CIDs or SIDs (Kim et al., 2019), again conserving source information. In order to link the data accurately to the previously discussed data layers, gene symbols are mapped to Ensembl Gene IDs (Hunt et al., 2018) through mygene.info (<http://mygene.info>) (Wu et al., 2013; Xin et

al., 2016). To provide a highly flexible data provisioning system, the UKS is stored as a graph database in Neo4j 4.0 (<https://neo4j.com/>), which allows to edit, retrieve and add new data as needed. The complete UKS contains 20793 human protein coding genes which are inter-linked by 5941639 edges, representing physical known interactions. Additional 7099 drugs are linked through 22973 edges to their genetic targets. To construct a high-quality gene-gene-network, gene-gene relationships, associated with a source support score of at least 0.75, are queried from the UKS and used to construct a single layer gene-gene-network, which is represented as a Python Networkx graph (Hagberg et al., 2008). The final gene-gene network is made up of 20793 nodes, representing Ensembl gene IDs, interlinked by 132244 high quality edges, describing interactions between the gene's associated proteins.

Shortest Paths

In order to identify the relevant genes that may have a crucial role in the progression of a SARS-CoV-2 infection, the shortest paths between the PI and the DE gene sets were computed. This analysis was performed for each group of DE genes identified in the different biological systems.

The shortest paths were retrieved with Python's NetworkX package (Hagberg et al., 2008) by running Dijkstra's shortest path algorithm (Dijkstra, 1959) between all possible pairs of PI and DE genes. All edges were considered to have equal weight, meaning that only the number of steps was considered when running the algorithm. Only paths consisting of at least one intermediate gene (IN) were considered during further analysis.

For each gene in the PPI network its occurrences as an IN between PI and DE was estimated separately for each experimental class and statistically significant enriched IN genes were identified. A hypergeometric test was performed, by comparing the IN frequencies identified in the shortest paths of interest, with their occurrences on all possible shortest paths in the complete gene-gene network. Adjusted p-values were estimated based on a Benjamin-Hochberg correction (Benjamini and Hochberg, 1995). The un-adjusted p-values were calculated with Python's scipy package (Virtanen et al., 2020) and the adjusted p-values were estimated based on the Python's stats models package (Seabold and Perktold, 2010).

Pathway Enrichment Analysis

In order to functionally characterize the lists of PIs, INs, and DEs, pathway enrichment analyses were performed using the Wikipathway 2019 Human database through the EnrichR online tool (Chen et al., 2013b; Kuleshov et al., 2016). The enriched pathways were visualized by means of the FunMappOne tool (Scala et al., 2019).

Gene Ranking

In order to evaluate the overall most common genes crossed in the shortest paths, for each *in vivo* and *in vitro* system, only statistical significant genes were selected and then ranked according to the intermediate gene count value. The five lists were given as an input to the *Borda* function of the *TopKList* R package (Schimek et al., 2015), to calculate the borda scores and rank the genes according to the median function.

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Author contributions

A.P. collected, integrated and analysed the raw data, developed the computational framework, drafted the manuscript; G.d.G. analysed and interpreted the results, drafted the manuscript; A.F. analysed the transcriptomics data and revised the manuscript; A.D.L. and P.A.S.K. interpreted the results and drafted the manuscript; A.S. supervised the development of the computational framework and revised the manuscript; D.G. conceived, designed and supervised the project; interpreted the results; revised the manuscript.

Declaration of Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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